

Reaction of Nitriles with Mercaptoacetic Acid. Facile Synthesis of Thiazolo[3,2-*a*]dihydropyridine and Thiazolo[4,5-*b*]pyran Derivatives

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2-Ethoxycarbonylmethyl-4-thiazolinone (1) reacted with 2 equivalents each of benzenediazonium chloride and benzaldehyde to afford 4-thiazolinone derivatives (2 and 3, respectively). Treatment of 3 with malononitrile, cyanoacetamide, ethyl cyanoacetate, benzoylacetonitrile and cyanoacetanilide gave thiazolo[3,2-*a*]dihydropyridine derivatives (4, 5, 6, 7 and 8, respectively). Azocyanoacetamide (9) reacted with mercaptoacetic acid in pyridine to yield 4-thiazolinone (10) which was condensed with ethyl 4-chlorobenzylidencyanoacetate (11) and 4-chlorobenzylidencyanoacetate (13) to furnish thiazolo[4,5-*b*]pyran derivatives (12 and 14, respectively).

BIOLOGICAL activities of azoles stimulated considerable attention on this class of compounds¹.

As part of a programme directed for developing newer procedures for synthesising ring systems containing pyrazole moiety² and in view of the reported biological activities³ of some thiazoles, 4-thiazolinone derivatives⁴ was reported from this laboratory. In continuation of that work, synthesis and reaction of some new 4-thiazolinone derivatives, are described here. It was found that 2-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-4-thiazolinone (1), readily prepared⁴ from mercaptoacetic acid and ethyl cyanoacetate, undergoes facile condensation with two equivalents each of benzenediazonium chloride and benzaldehyde to yield 2 and 3 respectively in reasonably good yield. Treatment of 3 with malononitrile in refluxing ethanol with catalytic amount of piperidine gave a solid product, m.p. 267°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400–3 300 (NH₂), 2 200 (CN), 1 730 (C=O ester) and 1 690 cm⁻¹ (amide or $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated C=O); δ 1.16 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.16 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.73 (2H, br s) and 7.3–7.9 (11H, m). Based on these evidences as well as elemental analyses, thiazolo[3,2-*a*]-1,4-dihydropyridine (4) structure was proposed for this compound. This was further confirmed by synthesising 4 from 1 and α -cyanocinnamionitrile in low yield. Mechanistically, initial Michael addition of malononitrile anion across α,β -unsaturated system at C-2 sidechain of 3 followed by nucleophilic attack by the imino nitrogen of the heterocyclic ring on one of the cyano groups of malononitrile, may be envisaged as the key steps of this transformation.

In order to explore the utility of this interesting cyclisation, 3 was treated under similar conditions with other nitrile containing active methylene compounds, viz. cyanoacetamide, ethyl cyanoacetate, benzoylcyanomethane and cyanoacetanilide

when respective thiazolo[3,2-*a*]-1,4-dihydropyridines (5–8) were isolated in good yield (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

It was also observed that mercaptoacetic acid reacts with azocyanoacetamide (9) in pyridine solution (Scheme 2) to yield 4-thiazolinone derivative (10) which could be condensed with ethyl 4-chlorobenzylidencyanoacetate (11) in ethanol with a catalytic amount of piperidine to give a solid (12), m.p. 270°. Based on elemental analysis and spectral data (ir, ¹H nmr), thiazolo[4,5-*b*]pyran

Scheme 2

structure was proposed for this compound. Reacting 10 in a similar way with 4-chlorobenzylidene-malononitrile (13) gave 14. Physical and spectral data of the compounds are summarised in Table 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-1100

spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Analytical data were obtained from Analytical Center, Cairo University.

Coupling reaction of benzenediazonium chloride with 2-ethoxycarbonyl methyl-4-thiazolinone (1): A solution of benzenediazonium chloride (0.02 mol) was poured slowly in a solution of 1 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (150 ml) containing sodium acetate (30 g) dissolved in water (50 ml) with continuous stirring at 0–5° for 1 h. It was then stirred at room temperature for 2 h and poured in ice-water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from benzene/petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to give red crystals of 4-thiazolinone derivative (2).

Reaction of benzaldehyde with 2-ethoxycarbonyl-methyl-4-thiazolinone (1): A solution of 1 (0.1 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed with benzaldehyde (0.2 mol) and piperidine (1 ml) for 3 h and then the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. The remaining product was triturated with ethanol and the resulting solid was recrystallised from chloroform to yield yellow crystals of 4-thiazolinone derivative (3).

Reaction of 3 with activated nitriles. General procedure: A solution containing equimolar amount (0.01 mol) of 3 and malononitrile, cyanoacetamide, ethyl cyanoacetate, benzoylacetoneitrile

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND IR AND PMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p.** °C (Solvent of crystal)	Yield %	Mol. formula	ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)	δ (ppm)
2	183 ^a	81	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	3 200–3 600 (NH), 1 722 (ester C=O), 1 700 (ring C=O), 1 640 (C=N)	1.2 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.1 (2H, q, CH ₂), 7.4–7.9 (10H, m), 8.2 (2H, br s, NH)
3	175 ^b	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₄ S	1 670–1 725 (ring C=O, ester C=O), 1635 (C=N)	1.21 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.0 (2H, q, CH ₂), 7.8–8.0 (12H, m)
4	267 ^c	70	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄ S	3 300–3 400 (NH ₂), 2 220 (ON), 1 730 (ester C=O), 1 690 (C=O)	1.16 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.16 (2H, q, CH ₂), 4.50 (1H, s, pyridine-OH), 6.73 (2H, br s, NH ₂), 7.3–7.9 (11H, m)
5	250 ^c	66	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	3 200–3 450 (NH ₂), 1 725 (ester C=O), 1 695 (ring C=O), 1 680 (CONH ₂)	Insoluble in common solvents
6	213 ^d	60	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	3 300–3 440 (NH), 1 700–1 730 (C=O, ester C=O), 1 670, 1 690 (C=N, C=O)	1.16 (6H, 2t, 2×CH ₃), 4.16 (4H, 2q, 2×CH ₂), 5.0 (1H, s, pyridine-OH), 6.33 (2H, br s, NH ₂), 7.3–7.9 (11H, m)
7	195 ^d	75	C ₁₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	3 400 (NH), 1 730 (ester C=O), 1 700 (ring C=O), 1 680 (C=O), 1 622 (C=O)	1.16 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.16 (2H, q, CH ₂), 5.01 (1H, s, pyridine-OH), 6.73 (2H, br s, NH ₂), 7.3–7.9 (16H, m)
8	250 ^c	73	C ₁₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	3 200–3 450 (NH ₂), 1 720 (ester C=O), 1 700 (ring C=O), 1 685 (CONH ₂)	1.16 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.1 (2H, q, CH ₂), 4.50 (1H, s, pyridine-OH), 6.7 (2H, br s, NH ₂), 7.3–8.0 (16H, m), 10.8 (1H, br s, NH)
10	270 ^c	63	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄ S	3 100–3 400 (NH), 1 690, 1 665 (C=O, CONH ₂)	Insoluble in common solvents
12	270 ^c	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ SCl	3 140–3 400 (NH, NH ₂), 1 695 (ester C=O), 1 660 (CONH ₂)	1.15 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.0 (2H, q, CH ₂), 5.1 (1H, s, pyran-OH), 6.65 (2H, br s, OH ₂), 7.3–8.2 (8H, m)
14	270 ^c	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₇ O ₄ SCl	3 000–3 400 (NH ₂), 2 200 (ON), 1 665 (CONH ₂)	Insoluble in common solvents

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, S and Cl analyses.
 ** Solvent for crystallisation: ^aBenzene–pet. ether, ^bCHCl₃, ^cEtOH–DMF, ^dEtOH.

or cyanoacetanilide in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed with piperidine (0.5 ml) for 3–6 h when a solid product separated. The solvent was then evaporated to half its volume and the resulting solid was crystallised from the proper solvent to yield pale-yellow crystals of thiazolo[3,2-*a*]dihydropyridine derivatives (4–8).

Reaction of p-nitrophenylazocycanoacetamide (9) with mercaptoacetic acid: A solution of 9 (0.1 mol; prepared as previously described⁴) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.1 mol) in pyridine (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h and the solvent was then partially evaporated and the mixture cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give orange crystals of 4-thiazolinone derivative (10).

Reaction of 10 with α,β -unsaturated nitriles (11 and 13): A suspension of an equimolecular amount (0.01 mol) of 10 and 11 or 13 in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed with piperidine (1 ml) for 5 h and then worked up as described in the reaction of 3 with activated nitriles. The resulting solid was

crystallised to yield thiazolo[4,5-*b*]pyran derivatives (12 or 14).

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